

Anhangsverzeichnis

In diesem Verzeichnis sind die im Rahmen der Arbeit "Aufbau von Ad-hoc WSN" angewandten Such- und Dokumentationsschritte ergänzend dargestellt. Die erste Tabelle dokumentiert die verwendete Suchstrategie, die sowohl KI-gestützt mit Elicit als auch über Datenbanken wie Scopus durchgeführt wurde. Für jede Suche werden dabei jeweils der finale Suchstring bzw. der verwendete Prompt angeführt. Ergänzend enthalten die Anmerkungen die zugehörigen Erstautorinnen und Erstautoren, den DOI sowie die konkrete Verwendung der jeweiligen Quelle in der vorliegenden Arbeit. Der zweite Abschnitt vertieft diesen Prozess exemplarisch anhand einer einzelnen Recherche und zeigt den Verlauf von der ersten Suchanfrage bzw. dem ersten Prompt bis zum final ausgewählten Ergebnis, konkret in Bezug auf das Paper von Ferreira et al. (2022) und das darin behandelte Modell für IoT-Projekte.

Suchstrategie

Tabelle 1. Suchstrategie

Nr.	Prompt / Suchbegriffe inklusive Bezeichnung und Verknüpfung	Anzahl gefundener Einträge	Anmerkungen
1	What shows the importance of Wireless Sensor Networks in context of Internet of things?	10	A: Kalyani DOI:10.31033/ijemr.13.6.1 IoT und Rolle WSN, WSN-Architektur
2	((("wireless ad hoc network" OR "wireless ad-hoc network" OR "wireless adhoc network" OR "ad hoc network" OR "ad-hoc network") AND (WSN OR "wireless sensor network") AND ("routing protocol" OR "routing protocols" OR routing) AND (survey OR review OR overview)))	220	A: Ghalib DOI: 10.1007/978-981-15-4451-4_3 Ad Hoc WSN, Routing
3	Which papers introduce IoT as a distributed, heterogeneous system concept?	10	A: Paolone DOI: 10.3390/iot3040022 +Rückwärtssuche

			(https://www.statista.com/statistics/1183457/iot-connected-devices-worldwide/)
			+Rückwärtssuche der Statista Quelle: https://transformainsights.com/research/forecast/highlights
			Aktuelle Marktprognose der IoT Entwicklung
4	What research explains why the increasing number of IoT devices require different network technologies or topologies instead of a single unified network architecture?	10	A: Qiu DOI:10.1109/COMST.2018.2803740
			Einleitung
5	What are recent studies discussing the growth of IoT devices and its impact on wireless sensor network development?	10	A: Yamini DOI:10.1016/j.measen.2024.101098
			Einleitung
6	((("internet of things" OR iot) AND topolog* AND (scalab* OR "power consumption" OR energ* OR delay OR latency OR synchroni* OR "error tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "device discovery") AND (review OR survey)))	261	A: De Masi DOI:10.1109/ICASET.2018.8376837
			Einleitung
7	(((mesh OR "mesh topology" OR "mesh network*" OR "multi-hop") AND ("wireless sensor network*" OR WSN* OR "sensor network*") AND ("ad hoc" OR adhoc OR "self-organiz*" OR "infrastructure-less") AND (architecture OR design OR	418	A: Shrestha DOI:10.1109/THS.2007.370059
			Topologien

	protocol* OR overview OR survey OR tutorial)) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Ad Hoc Networks"))		
8	What are the key routing protocols used in ad-hoc wireless sensor networks?	10	A: Haw DOI:10.1109/ICIAS49414.2021.9642695
9	((("wireless sensor network*" OR WSN OR "sensor network*") AND ("ad hoc" OR adhoc) AND (routingOR "routing protocol*" OR "routing algorithm*") AND ("state of the art" OR survey OR review)) AND PUBYEAR > 2019AND PUBYEAR < 2026	111	Routing, Einleitung A: Shah DOI:10.1007/s13198-025-02760-1 Routingprotokolle
10	(("neighbor discovery" OR "node discovery") AND ("wireless sensor network" OR WSN)) AND PUBYEAR > 2020 AND PUBYEAR < 2026	64	A: Mekala (2020) DOI: 10.4108/cai.27-10-2020.166772 Neighbor-Discovery +Rückwärtssuche: A: Carrano DOI:10.1016/j.adhoc.2013.12.009
11	What is the comparative energy consumption of AODV, DSDV, OLSR, and DSR routing protocols in ad hoc wireless sensor networks based on empirical studies?	10	Neighbor-Discovery A: Er-Rouidi DOI:10.1109/CGiV.2016.90
12	("scalability" OR "performance" OR "efficiency" OR "capacity") AND ("AODV" OR "Ad hoc On-Demand Distance	391	Energieeffizienz für OLSR;DSDV;AODV;DSR A: Ihbel DOI:10.1109/INTECH.2012.6457750

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|----|--|----|--|
| 13 | <p>Vector") AND ("DSDV"
OR "Destination-Sequenced
Distance-Vector") AND ("OLSR" OR "Optimized
Link State Routing") AND ("DSR" OR "Dynamic Source
Routing") AND ("ad hoc"
OR "wireless" OR "sensor
networks" OR "WSN")
AND ("evaluation" OR
"assessment" OR "analysis"
OR "comparison") AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Wireless Sensor Networks") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Ad Hoc Networks"))
("scalability") AND ("OLSR" OR "Optimized
Link State Routing") AND ("ad hoc" OR "wireless" OR "sensor networks" OR "WSN") AND PUBYEAR > 2014 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Olsr"))</p> | 33 | <p>Skalierbarkeit von AODV,
DSR, DSDV in WSN</p> <p>A: Jaggi
DOI:10.7232/iems.2016.15.3.259</p> <p>Skalierbarkeit von OLSR</p> |
| 14 | <p>(("AODV" OR "Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector" OR "routing protocol") AND ("OLSR" OR "Optimized Link State Routing" OR "routing algorithm") AND ("DSR" OR "Dynamic Source Routing" OR "routing method") AND ("DSDV" OR "Destination-Sequenced Distance-Vector" OR "routing technique") AND ("comparison" OR "evaluation" OR "analysis" OR "assessment")) AND PUBYEAR > 2017 AND PUBYEAR < 2027</p> | 91 | <p>A: Ahmed
DOI:10.52549/ijeei.v12i4.5761</p> <p>Robustheit & Latenz von Routing</p> |

15	(("wireless sensor network*" OR WSN) AND ("tree topology" OR "star topology" OR "mesh topology" OR "cluster topology") AND (compar* OR "comparative study" OR benchmark* OR "performance comparison"))	118	A: Rao DOI:10.1109/ICISC.2018.8399010 A: Mounika DOI:10.1109/ICISC.2018.8399050 Stern, Mesh, Baum, Cluster Vergleich
16	How do the U-Connect, SearchLight, and Disco neighbor discovery protocols perform in terms of discovery latency, accuracy, and resource consumption under non-ideal network conditions?	10	A: Kandhalu DOI:10.1145/1791212.1791253 U-Connect, Disco Energieeffizienz A: Camacho-Escoto DOI:10.3390/s21206822 Robustheit NDP
17	How do the SearchLight neighbor discovery protocols perform in terms energy consumption in wireless sensor networks?	10	A: Bakht DOI:10.1145/2348543.2348568 SearchLight Energieeffizienz
18	Durch Empfehlung (Vorgehensweise Scopus AI Prompt mit Titel „Ad-hoc networking case scenarios“)	1	A: Mukhedkar DOI:10.1109/ICCMC.2017.8282738 Katastrophenszenario

Suchprotokoll

Tabelle 2. Entwicklung der Suche zum Paper von Ferreira et al. (2022)

Nr.	Prompt / inklusive Bezeichnung und Verknüpfung	Suchbegriffe	Anzahl gefunden- er Einträge	Anmerkungen
1	When do organizations determine the most appropriate wireless sensor	organizations	10	Kein zufriedenstellendes Paper gefunden. Konzentrieren sich eher

	network technology during the initial stages of IoT project development?		auf verschiedene Technologien und ihre Kriterien
2	(("Internet of Things" OR IoT) AND ("decision-making" OR "decision model*" OR "decision support") AND (methodology OR framework)) AND PUBYEAR > 2019 AND PUBYEAR < 2027	220	Zu große Menge an Einträgen
2	(("Internet of Things" OR IoT) AND ("project development" OR "system development") AND ("decision-making" OR "decision model*" OR "decision support") AND (methodology OR framework)) AND PUBYEAR > 2019 AND PUBYEAR < 2027	21	Kein zufriedenstellendes Paper gefunden
2	(("Internet of Things" OR IoT) AND ("project development" OR "system development") AND (methodology OR framework OR "development process") AND (requirements OR design OR implementation)) AND PUBYEAR > 2019 AND PUBYEAR < 2027	141	Paper gefunden, durch Hinzunahme klassischer Projektphasen (Inspiration durch Wasserfallmodell)

Such Nr: 2

Journal: Internet of Things (Elsevier)

Titel: The Three-Phase Methodology for IoT Project Development

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Abstract. The development of IoT solutions requires the expertise from professionals from several areas. This multidisciplinary aspect can be better served with an integrated process to structure the development of these solutions. There are several software development methodologies, such as Ignite and ELDAMeth, that have been adapted for this end. However, most lack some fundamental functionalities. The Three-Phase Methodology for Project Development (TpM-Pro) was originally developed as an IoT teaching methodology that proved ideal for solution development. It is a generic, agile, interactive, technology- independent and

incremental methodology that splits the development of solutions into three distinct phases: Business, Requirements, and Implementation. This segmentation has proved invaluable and can become a standard for IoT solution development. In this paper, we present the Tpm-Pro, gauge it against five other methodologies proposed for IoT solution development and detail its application on a corporate IoT project.